

GENESIS, CLASSIFICATION AND AGRICULTURAL POTENTIAL OF THE SOILS DERIVED FROM KERRIKERRI SANDSTONE FORMATION IN NORTHERN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Genesis, classification and agricultural potentials of the soils derived from Kerrikerri sandstone formation in Bauchi State, Nigeria were investigated. Field and laboratory observations with the soils from five pedons, one each at crest, lower slope and valley floor, and two from middle slope positions, revealed that they were deep (>150 cm), brown (7.5YR 5/3) to very pale brown (10YR 7/3) and sandy loam to sandy clay loam in the upper horizon underlain by yellowish red (5RY 4/8) to brownish yellow (10YR 6/8) and gravely sand clay to clay horizons, with moderately well-developed sub-angular blocky structure and friable to very friable consistence. The soils were strongly to moderately acidic (pH. 5.1-5.9 in H₂O, 3.8-5.3 in CaCl₂), low in exchangeable bases (1.04 – 1.40 cmol (+) kg⁻¹ as well as exchange acidity (0.54 -1.90 cmol (+)kg⁻¹) with cation exchange capacity ranging between 4.4 and 27.6 cmol (+)kg⁻¹ soil. The dominant pedogenic processes influencing the rate of soil development were found to be clay lessivation, colluvial-fluvial deposition and neof ormation of minerals in the lower horizons as a result of downward leaching of the bases and likely better moisture condition at depth. The soils were classified according to the USDA Soil Taxonomy System (2003)/FAO-UNESCO Soil Map of the World Legend (1988) as Pedon 1 (Crest): Aquic Haplustult fine loamy, isomesic/Gleyic Acrisol, Pedons 2, 3 and 4 (Middle slopes 1 and 2 as well as Lower slope): Orthic Paleustults fine loamy kaolinitic, isohyperthermic/Orthic Acrisol, and Pedon 5 (Valley floor): Aquic Plinthic Haplustults clayey, isohyperthermic/ Plinthic Acrisol.

KEYWORDS: genesis, classification, agricultural potentials, sandstone, formation, lessivation.

INTRODUCTION

About 50% of Nigeria's geological land mass consists of sedimentary rocks (Fig. 1) mainly sandstone of Cretaceous age (Adeleye and Dessauvagie, 1970), part of the sediments lays roughly along the River Niger and Benue Basins. They are collectively referred to as Nupe and Bima sandstone, respectively. Within the Benue Trough, the sandstone is referred to as Bima or Gombe sandstone under which the Kerrikerri sandstone formation exists. It is composed of grit, shale, and clay (Carter *et al* 1963). The soils derived from Kerrikerri formation possess a great potential for increasing crop production through expansion of the cultivable area and adoption of improved agro-technology. One of the main requirements towards the opening up of new areas for intensive farming is a detailed characterization and mapping of the soils within a given land area. Such information is not much available for the study area and other areas with similar soils. This study was aimed to investigate the morphological as well as physico-chemical properties of the dominant soils in Gwaram area within the Kerrikerri sandstone formation, and to classify them according to Soil Taxonomy (Soil Survey Staff 2003) and the FAO/UNESCO (1988) World Soil Map Legend. Attempts have also been made to highlight the agricultural potentials of the soils and identify possible soil-related constraints to sustainable agricultural production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study Area

The area of study is located at Gwaram (10°15'N, 10° 20'E, 145m above sea level), some 8km south east of Alkaleri Town (10° 16'N, 10°20'E,) in the Alkaleri Local Government Area of Bauchi State, Nigeria. The Tertiary Sedimentary rocks consist of segment of flat -lying continental grits, sandstone and clays known as the Kerrikerri formation. They underlie the Kerrikerri Plateau and the Potiskum plain to the north (Dousse, 1969). Kerrikerri Plateau forms extensive rolling upstanding flat-topped Ironstone- capped relic hills. Bawden (1972) described the drainage pattern as widely spaced with stream lines as much as 1.6 km apart. In the north, tributary streams flow in narrow V-shaped valleys to the flood plain of the Gongola. Further south the Pai and its major

tributaries have flat-floored valleys bounded in most places by steep sides rising to the gentler plateau slopes. This formation occupies an area of 65,000 ha from which over 100 ha was investigated. The area is characterized by very deep and leached ferruginous soils previously identified as Ferralsols.

Receiving about 882 mm annual rainfall, the area has some 7 months (October – April) of dry season and diurnal temperatures averaging 31.6°C maximum and 13.1°C minimum. This puts the area in an isohyperthermic temperature regime. The area is situated in the Northern Guinea Savanna ecological zone with natural vegetation consisting of *Hyparrhenia*, *Riparia* spp and *Andropogon* as grasses, and scattered *Tamarindus indica*, *Parkia clapertoria* and *Khaya senegalensis* as the dominant trees. Some of the commonly cultivated agricultural crops are millet (*Pennisetum typhoideum* Rich), guinea corn (*Sorghum bicolor* L.), cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L.) and groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.).

Field Studies

Based on a reconnaissance survey using topographic and land-use approaches (free survey method), initially 36 sites were augured randomly to establish the kinds of soils in the area.

Subsequently, four soil units were identified as Unit 1 – Crest, Unit-2 Middle slope, Unit 3 – Lower slope and Unit 4 – Valley floor, One profile (pedon) pit was dug in each unit except the Unit 2- Middle slope where two pits (Middle slope –1 and Middle slope –2) were dug. Each profile was described according to the procedures outlined by the Soil Survey Staff (2002). A composite soil sample was collected from each recognizable pedogenic horizon in each profile.

Laboratory Studies

The soil samples were air- dried, crushed with a pestle and mortar and passed through a 2 – mm sieve. A 20g sub-sample of each was finely (<0.5mm,) ground and stored in a polythene bag for the estimation of organic carbon and total nitrogen. Each soil sample was analysed for various parameters included in Tables 2 to 4 using the methods as described by Page *et al.* (1982).

Briefly, the particle – size distribution was determined by the Bouyoucos hydrometer method and bulk density by the clod method; the latter was used to calculate the porosity assuming the particle density to be equal to 2.65Mgm⁻³. Soil pH (in 1:1 soil: water and 1:2 soil: CaCl₂ solution) was determined potentiometrically. The electrical conductivity of a 1:5 soil: water suspension was determined using a conductivity meter and the value multiplied by a conversion factor of 6.4 to obtain the EC of saturation extract as suggested by Landon (1991). Organic carbon and total nitrogen were respectively determined by the Walkley – Black wet combustion and macro-Kjeldahl digestion–distillation method. Bray No. 1 method was employed for the estimation of available phosphorus. Exchange acidity was estimated by the extraction with 1*m* KCl solution. Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined by the NH₄⁺ saturation method using the atomic absorption spectrophotometer; the values were used to calculate percentage base saturation. The cation exchange capacity of the minerals clay colloids was estimated by the equation:

$$\text{CEC (clay)} = \frac{\% \text{ Clay} \times (\text{CEC (soil)} - 3.5 \times \% \text{ OC})}{100} \times 100$$

Where, CEC = Cation exchange capacity in cmol (+) kg⁻¹ soil determined at pH 7.0, and OC = Organic carbon

This estimate is made on the assumption that 1% organic carbon accounts for an exchange capacity 3.5 cmol(+)⁻¹kg⁻¹ soil as empirically determined for the savanna soils by Sombrock and Zonneveld (1971).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphological Properties

Data on morphological features of the pedons are given in Table 1. The soils were deep to very deep, well-drained and sandy loam to sandy clay loam in the Ap horizon over a gravely sandy clay to clay subsurface horizons. This shows clearly the influence of parent materials especially in the surface horizons. The soil colour ranged from brown (7.5YR 5/3) to very pale brown (10YR 7/3) in the Ap horizons over yellowish red (5YR 4/8) to brownish yellow (10YR 6/8) subsurface horizons with moderate medium sub-angular blocky peds of friable to

very friable consistencies. Frequently, quartz grains were seen. Presence of a few ant and termite holes as well as nests indicated limited faunal pedoturbation within the soils. Pedon 5 (valley floor) had many nodules (10YR 8/1) of Fe and Mn with petroplinthic clay in the sub-soils which were also mottles.

Generally, there was an evidence of clay depletion in the surface horizons (Table 2). The lessivation appeared to have been promoted in these soils by the planar topography which enhances infiltration and consequently the effective rainfall. Pedon 1 showed the evidence of moderate drainage due to either accumulation of kaolinite or silty parent materials as shown by the high proportion of silt in this pedon (Table 2). There was a distinct disappearance of vegetative cover in the area. This may be due to kaolinite mining in the area which gives this unit (Pedon 1) a distinct local micro-relief and the land was left barren.

Physico-chemical Properties

Physical properties

Data in Table 2 show that with the exceptions of the horizons of lithologic discontinuity in Pedons 1 and 2 and B2v horizon of Pedon 4, sand was the dominant fine earth fraction in the soils indicating that the sandstone dominated the shale in the mixed parent materials. In pedon 1, silt was the dominant fraction in the last two horizons; in fact, the silt content in this pedon was generally higher than in the remaining pedons possibly due to higher content of shale as parent material. The higher clay content in the lowest horizons of pedons 2 and 4 as well as in all the sub-surface horizons of Pedons 5 may be attributed to clay lessivation and toposequential effect of the landscape more specifically in pedon 5, the Valley floor. These observations show a strong texture – parent material relationship and confirm the finding of Akamigbo and Asadu (1983) that the parent material dominates over climate as determinant of soil texture. The Ap horizon texture was sandy loam in the crest and middle slope positions and sandy clay loam in the lower slope position and valley floor. The texture in the sub-surface was variable except in pedon 5 (valley floor) where it was distinct clay (Table 2) indicating its accumulation through clay lessivation. There was general clay depletion in the Ap horizons as was observed by others before (Ojanuga and Awujoola 1981; Esu and Ojanuga 1985; Ojanuga 1995) working with the soils derived from sandstone parent materials. Such a depletion of clay in the upper layers may be attributed to the biological sorting of soil materials, clay migration and erosion (Ojanuga and Awujoola 1981).

Data in Table 2 further show that with exceptions in the Ap horizons of Pedons 4 and 5 and Bt1 horizon of Pedon 4, the silt: clay ratio was higher than the 0.15 limit reported by Van Wambeke (1962) to represent old parent materials. This indicates that the soil parent materials are old. The Weathering index silt: (silt+clay) was calculated to assess the degree of weatherability of silt and clay size particles in the soils. Young (1976) quoted that a ratio of <0.5 indicates less weathering. With this limit and the data on silt: (silt + clay) in Table 2 in view, it may be argued that the soils in the study area are highly weathered especially Pedons 1 – 3 (crest and middle slopes). While the lower slope and valley floor are less weathered as a result of fresh frequent materials deposit. It also depicts the consequence of interfluves on the soil units.

Bulk density values given in Table 2 show an appreciable variation among and within the soils units pointing to the differences in mineralogy, clay content and structural development. The values ranged from 0.87Mgm⁻³ to 1.53Mgm⁻³ in the Ap horizons and 1.12 to 1.94Mgm³ in the subsurface horizons. A relatively high bulk density recorded at the zone of lithologic discontinuities in some pedons may be related to a decrease in the pore space (Table 2) and possible concentration of iron oxide minerals into a gravelly layer. Good plant growth is obtained with bulk density below 1.4Mgm³ for clay soils and 1.6Mgm³ for sands (Donahue et al 1990). Further, a bulk density between 1.7 and 1.8 Mgm³ for sandy soils and between 1.45 and 1.65Mgm³ for clayey soils have been shown to inhibit root growth (Veighmeyer and Hendrickson 1948). With the Ap horizon bulk density

$<1.53\text{Mgm}^3$, the surface soils of the study area do not appear to offer any resistance to root penetration or growth. With the $0.42 - 0.67\text{m}^3\text{m}^{-3}$ porosity in the surface horizons, the soils appear to be favourable for good aeration, root penetration and free water movement. The porosity decreased gradually with depth to a value $\geq 0.27\text{m}^3\text{m}^{-3}$ owing to poor structure development in the subsurface horizons, e.g. in Pedons 2. Donahue *et al.* (1990) advocated that a porosity $<0.4\text{m}^3\text{m}^{-3}$ may affect root growth adversely.

Chemical properties

Data in Table 3 indicate that the soils were generally very strongly acidic with pH ranging from 4.1 to 5.9 in H_2O and 5.3 in CaCl_2 . The negative pH ($\text{pH}(\text{CaCl}_2) - \text{pH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$) values in Table 3 indicate that the soils contain positively charged minerals as suggested by Uehara and Gillman (1981). In the study area, the variable charge mineral may be dominantly kaolinite as it is mined locally. The high Al^{3+} content in the soils (Table 4) suggest that they contain some amount of reserve acidity.

The average saturation extract electrical conductivity of 0.59dSm^{-1} in Ap horizons and 0.43dSm^{-1} in sub-soils (Table 3) together with $<2\%$ exchangeable sodium percent (ESP) suggest that the salinization and sodication are not significant pedogenic processes and also calcification because of the acidic soil reaction ($\text{pH} < 6.0$). Raji *et al.* (1999) while working with the sand dunes, reported that calcification is not a major pedogenic process in the soils with $\text{pH} < 6.5$. These results tend to suggest that a rainfall of about 882mm/annum , an ustic moisture regime and high soil macroporosity prevalent in the study area are not conducive to salt accumulation in the soils (Table 4). In this regards, Buol *et al.* (1980) reported that a rainfall of about 760mm was just adequate for the leaching of bases in some Australian soils.

The data in Table 3 further show that the organic carbon content in all the pedons decreased irregularly with depth and was very low with the values being $< 10.0\text{gkg}^{-1}$ in the Ap horizons and $0.2 - 1.2$ (mean 0.6) gkg^{-1} in the subsurface horizons. Available phosphorus content ranged from low (1.3mgkg^{-1}) to high (28.2mgkg^{-1}) with an irregular pattern of vertical distribution. Farmers do apply phosphatic fertilizers in the area which might have been responsible for exceptionally high available P values ($>20\text{mgkg}^{-1}$) in some horizons (Table 3). The inherently low contents of organic matter mineralization, sparse natural vegetation inadequate return of crop residues, bush burning and short fallow period are associated with the low levels of available phosphorus and organic carbon.

Data in Table 4 show that the contents of exchangeable bases in the soils were quite low with the means (in $\text{cmol}(+) \text{kg}^{-1}$) of 0.20Ca , 0.19Mg , 0.20K and 0.10Na ; their magnitudes followed the order $\text{K} > \text{Ca} > \text{Mg} > \text{Na}$. This is contrary to the past findings that Ca and Mg are the dominant bases in the Nigerian savanna soils (Jones and Wild 1975, Ogunwale *et al.* 1975). It may be attributed to leaching losses of the bases and K- rich parent materials from which the soils mighty have developed. Further, it is evident from the data in Table 4 that the CEC values were low in pedon 2 (4.4 to $7.5\text{cmol}(+) \text{kg}^{-1}$ soil) up to the litholitic zone. In the other pedons, it varied from 7.2 (medium) to 27.6 (high) $\text{cmol}(+) \text{kg}^{-1}$ soil). Low CEC values have been reported for the savanna soils in the past (Ogunwale *et al.* 1975; Ojanuga, 1979). They attributed the low CEC values to low organic matter content and a variable charge nature of the clay minerals. The clay CEC data in Table 4 suggest that its values generally increased with depth in Pedons 1, 2 and 3; the vertical distribution was irregular in Pedons 4 and 5. Further, with a few exceptions most notably the horizons above 2Cv of Pedons, the clay CEC values were $>35\text{cmol kg}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of 2:1 layer silicate clay minerals besides kaolinite and Fe-oxyhydroxide as argued by Somebroek and Zonneveld (1971). Neofomation is most probable in the lower horizons as a result of downward leaching of the bases and likely better moisture condition at depth.

Exchangeable cations are part of the components of effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) and organic matter accounts for at least half of the CEC of surface soils (Agboola and Corey 1973). Sanchez (1976) advocated that any soil which has $<4\text{cmol}(+) \text{kg}^{-1}$ ECEC is less productive. The soils from all pedons possessed low ECEC within the range $1.18-2.80\text{cmol}(+) \text{kg}^{-1}$. Their base saturation ranged from 2 to 14% (mean 6%) indicating their low native productivity.

Soil Classification

As mentioned earlier, the soils of Gwaram in Alkaleri probably had an ustic soil moisture and isohyperthermic soil temperature regimes. The soils of pedons 2,3,4 and 5 have argillic horizons as confirmed by the presence of clay skins in Bt horizons (Table 1) and of clay bulges observed in the area, and have base saturation $<50\%$ (by neutral NH_4Oc extraction) which is considered equivalent to being $<35\%$ by the summation of cations (Sanchez, 1976). These soils may, therefore, be placed into the Order Ultisols of Soil Taxonomy (Soil Survey Staff 2003).

Owing to the ustic soil moisture regime, the soils are further classified into the Suborder Ustults. The soils of pedons 2, 3 and 4 are also thick reddish Ustults lacking plinthite that forms a continuous phase or constitutes more than half the matrix in any sub-horizon within 1.25m of the surface, They have argillic horizons in which the clay content does not decrease by as much as 20% from its maximum value within the depth of 150cm from the surface. These soils are, therefore, classified as Orthic Paleustults at the Great Group Level. These soils have control sections which are composed of more than 15% (by weight) of fine sand and more than 35% but less than 60% clay; thus, they are classified into the fine loamy particle-size class. Kaolinite constitutes more than half of the clay fraction in the soil units; therefore, they are classified at the Family level as Orthic Paleustults fine loamy kaolinitic, isohyperthermic. Pedon 5 (valley floor) has petroplinthite forming continuous layers within 150 cm depth and is classified at the Great Group level as Aquic plinthic Haplustult clayey, isohyperthermic. The Pedon1 was classified as Aquic Haplustult fine loamy kaolinitic, isomesic. The corresponding FAO/UNESCO (1988) classification is Orthic Acrisols for pedons 2, 3 and 4. Pedon 5 (valley floor) can be placed as Plinthic Acrisols and pedon 1 as Gleyic Acrisol.

Agricultural Potential of the Soils

Some good attributes of the soils under study coupled with fairly distributed available phosphorus status and friable consistency would pose no problems to tillage operation. They have good structure for adequate aeration, root penetration and free water movement.

However, the problems peculiar to the study area appear to be low organic matter content, high exchangeable aluminium which may cause phosphorus fixation, low CEC, deficiency of macro-nutrients especially N, Ca and Mg contents. The use of organic manures together with available inorganic fertilizers is therefore advocated for peasant farmers in the area.

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Table 1 Morphological features of the pedons

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Munsell colour (moist)	texture	structure	consistence	boundary	miscellaneous observation
Pedon 1 Crest							
Ag	0-5	7.5 YR 5/4	sl	2ccr	mfi	cs	plenty few coarse roots
Bs	5-16	10YR6/4	sl	2mgr	mfi	ds	few coarse root,
common medium hard fe/ Mn nodules							
2Btx	1 6-54	10R6/4	sl	2fcr	mfi	ds	Common few pores
2CB	54-110	7.5R6/3	sl	3msbk	mfi	cs	few microporse kaolin accumulation
3C2g	110-150+	7.5Y8/1. *7.5Y8/1	sl	3msbk	mfi	cs	few microporse
Pedon 2 Middle Slope- 1							
Ap	0-15	7.5 YR 5/3	sl	1fsbk	mfr	cs	common fine root, few micropores
BA	15-38	7.5YR 4/4	sl	2cr	mfr	cs	Many fibrous roots, few macropores, clay skins
Bt1	38-90	5YR 4/6	sl	2cr	mfr	ds	few fibrous coarse roots, few micropores
Bt2	90-110	5YR 4/8	sl	2cr	mfi	ds	few fibrous coarse root, few micropores
BCc	110-140	5YR 5/8	sd	2mgr	mfi	ds	Few micropores
2Cv	140-180	5 YR 5/8	sc	2cgr	mfi	cs	Few micropores, kaolinite deposit
Pedon 3 Middle Slope-2							
Ap	0-18	10YR 6/2	sl	1fcr	mvfr	ds	Many medium pores, many medium fibrous roots
Bt1	8-38	10YR5/3	l	2fcr	mfr	cs	Few fine roots, common few pores
BA	38-62	10YR6/4	sl	2mcr	mvfr	cs	Few common pores, day skin few medium hand
Fe/nodules							
Bt2	62-86	10YR6/8	scl	2mabk	mvfr	cs	Medium many pores, day skin
Bt3	86-130	2.5YR 5/8	scl	3fsbk	mvfr	cs	Fine common
pores							
C	130-200	2.5 YR 5/8	ls	3mabsk	mvfr	cs	Common medium pores

TABLE 1 continued

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Munsell colour (Moist)	texture	structure	consistence	boundary	miscellaneous observations
Pedon 4: lower slope							
Ap hole	0-9	10YR 7/3	scl	1mcr	mvfr	gs	plenty fibrous roots, common macropores few ant
EB	9-32	10YR 6/3	scl	1mgr	mvfr	gs	Many fibrous roots, macropores
Btl	32-70	10YR 6/8	scl	1mcr	mvfr	gs	Few coarse and fibrous roots, common macropores
Bt2	70-97	7.5YR7/8	scl	2mcr	mvfr	gs	Very few fibrous roots, a few macropores
B2v medium Fe/Mn nodules	97-168+	2.5YR 4/8	c	3 csbk	mfi	cs	Macropores, a few animal activities, common
Pedon 5: Valley Floor							
Ap roots, micropores	0-11	7.5YR 5/3	sc	1fcr	mfr	gs	A few medium krotorians activities, common fibrous
Btl roots	11-33	7.5 YR4/6	c	2 fcr	mfr	gs	Macropores, many fibrous roots with few coarse
Bt2 nodules	33-100	5YR 6/7*5YR 5/1	c	3 csbk	mfi	gs	Few very fine roots many pores many Fe/ Mn
2Btv petroplinthite below	100-180+	7.5 YR5/6 * 10YR 8/1	c	3mabk	mfr	cs	Clay skin, many medium pores. many nodules

** Symbols as in soil survey Manual (Soil Survey Staff 2002)* Mottle Colour

Table 2 some physical properties of the pedons

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Soil separate			Texture	Si:C ratio	Si(Si+C) ratio	BD (Mgm ⁻³)	Porosity (M ⁻³ m ⁻³)
		Sand	Silt	Clay					
Pedon 1: Crest									
Ag	0-5	61	25	14	sl	0.79	0.64	1.53	0.42
Bs	5-10	60	13	22	sl	0.82	0.45	1.16	0.56
2Btx	16-54	50	24	20	sl	0.92	0.48	1.28	0.52
2CB	54-110	36	56	03	sl	7.00	0.88	1.52	0.43
3C2g	110-150+32		60	08	sl	7.50	0.88	1.60	0.40
Pedon 2: Middle Slope-1									
Ap	0-15	70	17	12	sl	1.42	0.59	0.87	0.67
BA	15-38	59	23	18	sl	1.28	0.56	1.68	0.37
Btl	38-90	63	19	18	sl	1.06	0.51	1.61	0.39
Bt2	90-110	41	27	32	scl	0.84	0.46	1.94	0.27
BCc	110-140	61	19	20	sl	0.95	0.49	1.51	0.43
2Cv	140-180	12	31	57	c	0.54	0.35	1.16	0.56
Pedon 3: Middle slope-2									
Ap	0-18	65	18	17	sl	1.06	0.51	1.45	0.45
Btl	18-38	62	12	27	l	0.44	0.31	1.24	0.53
BA	38-62	63	18	19	sl	0.95	0.49	1.43	0.46
Btz	62-80	40	16	38	scl	0.42	0.30	1.30	0.51
Bt3	86-130	44	22	35	scl	0.63	0.39	0.46	0.45
C	130-200+67		24	09	sl	2.67	0.73	1.36	0.49
Pedon 4: Lower slope									
Ap	0-9	70	01	29	scl	0.03	0.03	1.25	0.53
EB	9-32	66	05	29	scl	0.17	0.15	1.26	0.52
Btl	32-70	64	03	33	scl	0.09	0.08	1.32	0.50
Bt2	70-79	62	07	31	scl	0.23	0.18	1.12	0.58
B2v	97-168+	28	13	59	c	0.22	0.18	1.14	0.57
Pedon 5: Valley floor									
Ap	0-11	62	03	35	scl	0.09	0.08	1.42	0.48
Btl	11-33	36	23	41	c	0.56	0.36	1.35	0.49
Bt2	33-400	42	11	47	c	0.23	0.19	1.32	0.50
2Btv	100-180+38		13	49	c	0.27	0.21	1.85	0.30

sl = sandy loam, sil=silt loam, l=loam, c=clay, scl=sandy clay loam, ls=loamy sand BD=bulk density

TABLE 3:
Some chemical properties of the pedons

Horizon	Depth (cm)	pH			EC (dsm ⁻¹)	Organic C (gkg ⁻¹)	Total N (gkg ⁻¹)	Avail P (mgkg ⁻¹)
		1:1H ₂ O	CaCl ₂	dpH				
Pedon 1: Crest								
Ag	0-5	4.4	4.3	±0.1	0.74	74	0.7	28.2
Bs	5-16	5.1	4.2	±0.9	0.52	2.0	1.0	12.1
2Btx	16-54	4.2	4.0	±0.2	0.54	4.8	0.7	4.2
2CB	54-110	4.3	4.0	±0.3	0.43	2.4	1.0	8.9
3C2g	110-150+4.5		3.8	±0.7	0.41	1.2	0.9	4.2
Pedon 2: Middle Slope-1								
Ap	0-15	5.9	5.3	±0.6	0.74	3.4	35	8.2
BA	15-38	5.4	4.2	±1.2	0.55	3.8	0.3	2.1
Btl	38-90	5.3	4.4	±0.9	0.46	2.0	0.6	1.8
Bt2	90-110	5.1	4.3	±0.8	0.51	2.0	0.2	1.3
BCc	110-140	5.2	4.5	±0.7	0.53	1.8	0.3	5.6
2Cv	140-180	5.3	4.6	±0.7	0.42	1.8	1.6	29.4
Pedon 3: Middle slope-2								
Ap	0-18	4.6	3.8	±0.8	0.42	3.6	1.0	2.8
Btl	18-38	4.9	3.9	±1.0	0.46	2.5	0.7	18.2
BA	38-62	4.9	4.0	±0.9	0.53	3.0	1.0	23.8
Bt2	62-86	4.8	4.0	±0.8	0.47	0.42	1.2	3.4
Bt3	86-130	4.6	3.9	±0.7	0.45	1.8	0.9	7.0
C	130-200+45		3.9	±0.6	0.48	1.6	1.2	11.2
Pedon 4: Lower slope								
Ap	0-9	5.3	4.6	±0.7	0.53	4.2	0.4	3.2
EB	9-32	5.1	4.2	±0.9	0.51	1.6	0.2	70
Btl	32-70	5.0	4.4	±0.6	0.46	1.4	0.2	42
Bt2	70-79	5.3	4.5	±0.8	0.56	0.8	0.3	28
B2v	97-168+	4.1	3.8	±0.3	0.52	1.8	0.7	26.8
Pedon 5: Valley floor								
Ap	0-11	5.0	4.3	±0.7	0.54	3.0	0.6	82
Btl	11-33	4.9	4.1	±0.8	0.45	2.0	0.7	16.8
Bt2	33-400	5.1	4.2	±0.9	0.47	20	07	8.4
2Btv	100-180+5.2		4.2	±1.0	0.55	1.6	04	5.6

pH=+ with(pH H₂O-pH CaCl₂) EC=electrical conductivity of saturation extract =-with (pH CaCl₂-pH H₂O)

Table 4 Exchange properties of the pedons

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Exchangeable (cmol(+)kg ⁻¹)				EA (cmol(+)kg ⁻¹)	Al (cmol(+)kg ⁻¹)	Soil	CEC Clay	ECEC (cmol(+)kg ⁻¹)		Base saturation (%)	
		Ca	Mg	K	Na					Soil	Clay	CEC	ECEC
Pedon 1: Crest													
Ag	0-5	0.15	0.27	0.35	0.11	0.88	0.72	7.2	37.2	1.77	*	11	50
Bs	5-16	0.30	0.27	0.12	0.09	1.66	1.50	11.2	47.7	2.44	7.91	7	22
2Btv	16.54	0.17	0.09	0.08	0.14	0.70	0.26	22.8	81.2	1.18	*	2	41
2CB	54.110	0.29	0.09	0.42	0.15	0.54	0.54	24.4	294.3	1.49	8.13	4	64
3C2g	110-150+	0.31	0.09	0.10	0.06	2.22	1.48	27.4	337.3	2.80	29.75	2	21
Pedon 2: Middle slope-1													
Ap	0.15	0.11	0.23	0.17	0.09	1.70	1.28	4.4	26.8	2.30	9.25	14	26
BA	15.38	0.11	0.25	0.08	0.08	1.44	1.08	4.6	38.2	1.98	3.61	12	27
Btl	38.90	0.15	0.21	0.16	0.02	1.18	0.52	5.0	23.9	1.72	5.67	11	31
Bt2	90-110	0.12	0.29	0.06	0.10	0.94	0.66	8.1	23.1	1.51	2.53	7	38
BCc	110-140	0.22	0.34	0.23	0.10	1.40	0.96	7.5	34.4	2.29	8.30	12	38
2Cv	140-180	0.20	0.33	0.11	0.09	1.22	1.00	27.0	46.3	1.95	2.23	3	37
Pedon 3: Middle slope-2													
Ap	0-18	0.18	0.12	0.27	0.11	1.06	1.06	6.4	30.2	1.74	2.82	11	39
Bt1	18-38	0.30	0.09	0.04	0.09	1.00	0.76	15.2	52.9	1.88	3.59	6	47
BA	38-62	0.30	0.08	0.31	0.08	0.80	0.78	16.8	82.9	1.57	2.74	5	71
Bt2	62-86	0.16	0.29	0.30	0.16	1.42	1.06	17.2	43.1	2.33	3.92	5	39
Bt3	86-130	0.03	0.24	0.08	0.06	1.32	1.16	20.2	55.9	2.02	3.97	3	35
C	130-200+	0.11	0.16	0.13	0.14	0.92	0.52	22.6	244.9	1.46	10.00	2	37

*=Values were negative

TABLE 4 (Continued)

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Exchangeable (cmol(+)kg ⁻¹)				EA Al cmol(+)kg ⁻¹	CEC		ECEC cmol(+)kg ⁻¹		Base saturation (%)		
		Ca	Mg	K	Na		Soil	Clay	Soil	Clay	CEC	ECEC	
Pedon 4: Lower slope													
Ap	0-9	0.12	0.22	0.19	0.11	1.60	1.20	17.4	54.9	2.24	2.66	4	29
EB	9-32	0.12	0.12	0.24	0.07	1.04	0.96	11.6	38.1	1.59	3.55	5	35
Bt1	32-70	0.12	0.11	0.29	0.10	0.16	1.04	19.6	57.9	1.78	3.91	3	35
Bt2	70-97	0.26	0.13	0.26	0.11	1.34	0.54	24.4	294.3	1.49	8.13	4	64
B2v	97-168+	0.23	0.11	0.13	0.12	1.74	1.34	27.6	45.7	2.33	2.88	2	25
Pedon 5: Valley floor													
Ap	0-11	0.25	0.15	0.28	0.07	1.72	0.70	19.0	51.3	1.47	1.20	4	51
Bt1	11-33	0.12	0.15	0.05	0.08	1.76	0.54	25.6	60.7	2.16	3.56	2	19
Bt2	33-100	0.15	0.29	0.32	0.12	1.28	1.04	13.6	27.0	2.16	2.66	10	41
2Btv	100-180+0.18	0.29	0.14	0.13	1.14	1.08	1.08	21.4	42.5	1.88	2.69	7	39

EA = Exchange acidity (Al^{3++H+}), Al³⁺= Aluminium concentration, CEC = Cation exchange capacity, ECEC = Effective CEC

Fig 1. Geological map of Nigeria showing sampling site
Source: Adeleye and Dessauvage (1970)

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